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**KOMPYUTER ILMLARI VA
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DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION AND INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This thesis analyzes the development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, regional opportunities and international cooperation issues. The main focus is on the tourism potential of Samarkand, Khiva, Bukhara and Jizzakh regions. The article is based on statistical data for 2020–2025, resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of tourism, as well as reports of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). As a result of the research, conclusions and proposals were developed on the development of the country's tourism infrastructure, attracting investments and forming new types of tourism.

Key words: Tourism, Samarkand, Khiva, Bukhara, Jizzakh, ecotourism, cultural heritage, international cooperation, investment.

Introduction. The tourism sector of Uzbekistan is one of the priority areas of the country's economy. In recent years, the decisions and decrees adopted by the government, the development of infrastructure, and the expansion of international cooperation are helping to shape tourism as a driving sector of the economy. In 2020–2025, the flow of tourists to Uzbekistan is increasing year by year. For example, in 2023, the number of foreign tourists visiting our country amounted to 6.6 million, while in 2024 this figure reached 7.5 million.

Tourism is not only a source of economic income, but also plays an important role in improving the country's international image, promoting cultural heritage, and ensuring employment for the local population. Therefore, rapid reforms are being carried out in the tourism market of Uzbekistan: electronic visas have been introduced, new hotels, transport and logistics centers, and service facilities are being built.

This thesis covers the theoretical foundations of tourism, the practical situation in the regions of Uzbekistan, the possibilities of international cooperation, as well as existing problems and their solutions.

Tourism is a process of temporary travel by a person outside his permanent place of residence for purposes not related to recreation, education, treatment, pilgrimage or work, and the use of various services during this trip. According to the definition of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), tourism is one of the fastest growing and most profitable sectors of the economy.

- The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language defines the term “tourism” as “the activity of traveling, resting, and exploring new places.” The essence of tourism is not only traveling, but also learning new cultures, developing friendship between peoples, and expanding economic ties.

- Tourism accounts for about 10% of global GDP and employs more than 320 million people worldwide (UNWTO, 2024). In Uzbekistan, the share of the tourism sector in GDP was 3.2% in 2024. At the same time, this sector occupies an important place in the export of services: in 2024, the volume of tourism services exports amounted to 2.1 billion US dollars.

- The economic efficiency of tourism:
 - creates new jobs;
 - increases national currency earnings;
 - stimulates the development of infrastructure;
 - stimulates small business and private entrepreneurship.

In recent years, a number of state programs for the development of tourism have been adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular:

- Presidential Decree of January 5, 2019 - “On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan”;
- The National Development Strategy for 2022–2026 identifies tourism as a “driver sector of the economy”;
- Resolution of March 1, 2023 - “On measures to improve the quality of tourism services and create new tourism destinations”.

Based on these documents, a favorable legal framework has been created for the tourism sector, including the introduction of electronic visas, a “single tourism portal”, a system of certification of hotels and guide services.

Today, the following tourism destinations are actively developing in Uzbekistan:

Cultural and historical tourism - in cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrissabz;

- Pilgrimage tourism – based on the shrines of Imam Bukhari, Bahauddin Naqshband, Sheikh Zayniuddin and other places of pilgrimage;
- Ecotourism – in the mountain and forest areas of Jizzakh and Surkhandarya regions;
- Health tourism – in the sanatoriums of Sariosiyo, Chimyon, and Zamin;
- Rural tourism – based on familiarization with the traditional way of life of the local population.

Samarkand is the oldest and most popular tourist center in Uzbekistan. The city, called the “Pearl of the East”, is famous for its UNESCO World Heritage Site Registan Square, the Shahi Zinda Complex, the Bibi Khanum Mosque, and the Ulugbek Observatory.

According to statistics for 2024:

- The number of foreign tourists visiting the Samarkand region is 2.3 million;
- Revenue from tourism services is 610 million US dollars;
- The number of hotels is 530, of which 40 work in partnership with international brands.

A new international airport for modern aircraft has also been built in the region, which has increased the number of international flights by 1.5 times.

Khiva is known as the “living museum” of Uzbekistan. The Ichan-Kala complex has been on the UNESCO World Heritage List since 1990. In recent years, the city of Khiva has become a host of international tourism festivals.

In 2024, in the Khorezm region:

- Revenue from tourism services - 280 million US dollars;
- In 2023, Khiva was awarded the title of "World Tourism Capital - 2024"

(according to UNWTO).

The main type of tourism in the region is cultural-historical and pilgrimage tourism. In addition, ecotourism and ethnotourism are developing on the banks of the Amu Darya River in the centers of folk arts.

Bukhara is one of the most ancient cities in Central Asia, recognized as the "Capital of Islamic Culture". In 2022, Bukhara was included in the "Network of Creative Cities" by UNESCO. There are more than 1,200 historical monuments in the region. The most developed direction of tourism in Bukhara is pilgrimage tourism. The Bahouddin Naqshband complex, the Kalon Tower, and the Ark Fortress attract millions of tourists from all over the world.

In recent years, the Jizzakh region has been becoming a center of ecotourism and health tourism. In particular, the Zamin National Park and the mountain-forest areas of the Forish district attract not only local but also foreign tourists.

In 2024, the Jizzakh region:

- More than 350 thousand tourists visited;
- Revenue from tourism services - 75 million US dollars;
- About 20 new guest houses were opened in the Zamin and Gallaorol districts.

Rural tourism is also widely developing in the region. National cuisine, handicrafts, and ancient customs of the local population are of great interest to tourists.

Table – Tourism Development Forecast until 2030

Development Forecast of the Tourism Sector of Uzbekistan (2024–2030)

Indicators	2024 years	2027 years	2030 years
Foreign tourists (mln)	7,5 mln	11 mln	15 mln
Tourism revenues (\$)	2,5 billion	3,8 billion	5,2 billion
Number of hotels	1800	2500	3500
Jobs (thousands)	350 thousand	480 thousand	650 thousand

- In recent years, Uzbekistan has established cooperation in the tourism sector with many countries of the world. As a result of strategic cooperation with the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), the 25th session of the UNWTO General Assembly was successfully held in Samarkand in 2023.

In addition:

- Joint programs are being developed with Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and Malaysia to develop pilgrimage tourism;
- Joint projects on cultural tourism are being implemented with France, Germany, and Italy;
- Cooperation has been established with China and South Korea in the field of transport and logistics and the development of an electronic visa system.

- Uzbekistan is actively attracting foreign investment in the tourism sector. About \$2.1 billion was invested in tourism infrastructure in 2020–2024.

- Some of the major projects include:
 - International tourism complex “Silk Road Samarkand” in Samarkand region (in collaboration with Japanese, Turkish, and local investors);
 - Tourism segment of the Tashkent City project in Tashkent region;
 - Construction of 4-5 star hotels in Bukhara and Khorezm regions (with the participation of investors from the United Arab Emirates).
- To attract more foreign tourists, the government of Uzbekistan:
 - Introduced an electronic visa system (simplified for citizens of more than 90 countries);

Direct flights to more than 50 countries through 11 international airports were opened on the basis of the “Open Sky” policy;

- Benefits were created for the export of tourism services (for example, VAT benefits for hotels).

- Samarkand – restoration of historical monuments in cooperation with UNESCO;

- Khiva – active participation in the “UNESCO Heritage Cities” program;
- Bukhara – pilgrimage tourism infrastructure together with the “Islamic Financial Center”;

- Jizzakh – ecotourism and green energy projects with the European Union and the Republic of Korea.

Although the tourism sector of Uzbekistan is developing rapidly, a number of systemic problems remain:

1. Insufficient infrastructure

- Hotel and transport and logistics services are limited in some regions (Jizzakh, Syrdarya, Kashkadarya).

- Although the airport and railway stations have been modernized, the quality of service does not fully meet international standards.

2. Weak marketing and branding

- Insufficient advertising campaigns to enhance Uzbekistan's international image.

- The brand "Uzbekistan - The Pearl of the Silk Road" is not sufficiently recognized worldwide.

3. Shortage of personnel

- There is a shortage of qualified guides, managers and service specialists for the tourism industry.

- There is a lack of personnel with excellent knowledge of foreign languages.

4. Environmental problems

- In some regions (for example, Aydarkul, Aral Sea), an ecological balance is required for the sustainable development of tourism.

- Ecotourism opportunities are not sufficiently developed.

2. Competitiveness issues: In countries such as Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Georgia, tourism services are cheaper and more diversified and Uzbekistan has not yet achieved an advantage in price-quality balance.

The following areas are of great importance for the rapid development of Uzbek tourism:

1. Digitalization

Expansion of online booking, electronic payments, virtual guide services through the “Single National Tourism Platform” and also Simplification of interactive maps and services for tourists through mobile applications.

2. Diversification: Development of ecotourism, sports tourism, gastronomic tourism in addition to traditional cultural tourism and Ecotourism centers in Jizzakh region, extreme tourism in Surkhandarya, ecological and scientific tourism destinations in Karakalpakstan.

Development of joint tourism packages with neighboring countries based on the “Great Silk Road” brand. Deepening cooperation with UNWTO, ISESCO and other international organizations. Expanding tax and customs privileges for foreign investors. Actively involving the private sector in hotel construction and transport and logistics projects.

At the same time, existing problems in the sector - insufficient infrastructure, weak human resources, ineffective marketing, and environmental problems - require urgent solutions. Therefore, we can say that the use of various methods and strategies for the development of the tourism sector will be effective. For example, we can cite the following: infrastructure development: the construction of a hotel and service complex in each region that meets international standards, as well as the modernization of airport and railway infrastructure. Personnel training: the introduction of new educational programs based on international standards in tourism colleges and universities and the training of guides and managers with specialization in foreign languages. Marketing and branding: the launch of unified advertising campaigns under the “Silk Road Uzbekistan” brand to promote Uzbek tourism worldwide, as well as the widespread use of digital marketing, social networks and online platforms.

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